

NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF TRI-BODY COMPOSITES

BOAT BY VARTM INTEGRAL FORMING PROCESS

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ABSTRACTS

With the development of science and technology, variety of composite manufacturing processes emerged as the times required. The vacuum assisted resin transfer molding (VARTM) process is now used extensively in the aerospace engineering, ship and ocean engineering and civil engineering due to the advantages such as the high efficiency, low cost and non-pollution. The object of this paper is to get a reliable and efficient approach to simulate the full-scale and complex sandwich composite structures. In this paper, the formula of computation of the fiber permeability was derived on the base of Darcy's law and the fiber permeability is calculated by the formula at first, then the VARTM integral forming process of a tri-body composites boat model was simulated by RTM-Worx software. For the convenience of engineering analysis, the tri-body composites boat model was divided into the upper and lower half. Furthermore, the two halves were also simplified in RTM-Worx. After that, two mold filling schemes were given and contrasted to get the optimal mold filling scheme. On this basis, in order to simulate the flow process of resin in the sandwich composites with foam core, the method for filling the sandwich structure mold was given by the software. The diversion trenches and the diversion conduits on the foam core are replaced by circular runners in this method. Simulation results show that the symmetric arrangement of the runner is helpful to avoid dry spots and save the resin. In a word, through the optimization of mold filling scheme and the simulation for the tri-body composites boat model, this paper provide a feasible approach for simulating the full-scale and complex sandwich composites with foam core.

1. INTRODUCTION

The process of science and technology promotes the rapid development of new materials, especially in the development of composites. Because they have a series of advantages, such as the lightweight of structure, high specific strength and modulus, anti-fatigue, thermostability, vibration attenuation and designable behaviour, composites have been

extensively used in many fields in recent decades, including aerospace, shipbuilding, automobile and so on.

With the development of forming technology of composites, RTM (Resin Transfer Moulding) gradually gets the favor of people because it not only can get large and complex structure parts integrated, but also undertake products' overall forming. On the basis of this technology, the developing technology of VARTM (Vacuum Assistance Resin Transfer Moulding), having the features of excellent manufacturability, low cost, good environmental protection and so on, is widely used in civil and national defense industry.

International scholars have done a lot of work about the computer simulating calculation of VARTM. Chengsong Dong, working in Curtin University in Australia, adopted the two-step method to improve the efficiency of computer process simulation^[1]; Ajit R.Nalla and the others proved that closed-loop control has more potential values and benefits than open-loop control by simulating and researching different filling lines used to configure all kinds of models through the usage of computer programming on the basis of finite element algorithm as well as comparing with various experiments^[2]; JONATHAN put forward a method of effective-medium theory (EMM), which demonstrates that the simulation of EMM has higher accuracy and faster calculation speed than the traditional method of Control Volume Finite Element Method (CVFEM) by comparing them and analyzing relevant examples^[3]; Netherlandish W.D.Brouwer and others demonstrated that the selection of injection tools and materials as well as the difference of injection plans has a greater influence on the quality of the final forming components through the VARTM on big fan blades which are structurally simple and the body of a ship by RTM-Wrox software, which leads to the conclusion that if you want to produce components with good quality, you ought to choose the suitable tools and materials and use the best injection plans to do injection^[4]; Fuhong Dai, Boming Zhang and others, working in Harbin Engineering University of China, had written their own simulation program named SHELLCV about the process of mould-filling in RTM, which not only can effectively predict the peak flow of the resin flow and the distribution of pressure field at any time by calculating and simulating the filling process of cylinder, i-beam and the contact plate of cars, but also provide effective reference for the design of craft process, including the arrangements of gates and vents, mold clamping pressure, etc^[5].

2. INTRODUCTION OF METHODS AND MODELS

2.1 Calculation Principles of RTM-Wrox Software

According to Darcy's law, RTM-Wrox is a kind of software used for simulated analysis of RTM processing through the calculation of flow equation while resin flowing in porous medium by using the method of finite element algorithm. The software combines the analysis of finite element algorithm and the core of volume envelope calculation together, which can get the accurate results in a relatively short period of time. During the simulated process, we can directly set technological parameter, install the locations of gates and vents as well as the distribution of pipelines. Moreover, it can be used for simulating various complex parts and viewing the peak flow of the resin flow and the distribution of pressure field at any time so as to predict the filling time of moulding and the locations where may occur to some dry spot defects, which provides more effective reference for the design of VARTM process^[6].

The flow of resin through a reinforcement is well described by Darcy's Law, which predicts a linear relation between the local flux density and the applied pressure gradient. With gravity terms included, Darcy's Law generalized to three dimensions and the continuity equation are:

$$\underline{u} = -\frac{K}{\eta} (\nabla p - \rho_r \underline{g}) \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \underline{u} = 0 \quad (2)$$

In these two formulas, \underline{u} is used for local heat flux, \underline{K} for the tensor of permeability, η for resin's viscosity, p for internal pressure of resin, ρ_r for the density of resin and \underline{g} for the gravity vector. While putting formula (2) into formula (1), we will get the continuous equation that resin flows in moulds, in which there's only an unknown quantity, as shown like formula (3).

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{K}{\eta} (\nabla p - \rho_r \underline{g}) \right) = 0 \quad (3)$$

According to the different actual situation, we can introduce different boundary conditions and initial conditions, as shown in figure 1, so as to find the solution of formula (3)^[6].

Figure 1. A mould cavity being filled, forming a domain with boundaries

2.2 Simulation Model

Figure 2 shows the simulation model of the hull of this paper, where the overall dimensions of the hull is shown. In figure 2(a), the thickness of sector A is set for 1.2mm and sector B for 1mm. In figure 2(b), the thickness of sector C is set for 1.2mm, sector D for 1.8mm and sector E for 1.4mm. The whole body of this ship is foam sandwich structure, whose thickness is 30mm.

Figure 2 Simulation Model of The Hull and Its Dimensions

3. SIMULATION AND OPTIMIZATION

3.1 The Determination of Simulation Parameters

The filling process of RTM can be regarded as the flow of viscous fluid in porous medium, which is usually described by Darcy's law.

$$v = -\frac{k}{\mu} \cdot \Delta P \quad (4)$$

In this formula, v is used for the flow velocity of liquid, k for permeability, μ for the viscosity of liquid and ΔP for the pressure difference. On this basis, J.R.Weitzenbock and others deduced the calculation formula about the anisotropy of permeability along the major axis:

$$K_{11} = \left[x_f^2 \left(2 \ln \frac{x_f}{x_0} - 1 \right) + x_0^2 \right] \cdot \frac{1}{t} \cdot \frac{\mu \varepsilon}{4 \Delta P}$$

$$K_{22} = \left[y_f^2 \left(2 \ln \frac{y_f}{y_0} - 1 \right) + y_0^2 \right] \cdot \frac{1}{t} \cdot \frac{\mu \varepsilon}{4 \Delta P} \quad (5)$$

In this formula, K_{11} is used for the direction permeability of X, and K_{22} is for Y. x_0 is the radius of gates on the X direction, y_0 is on the Y direction. x_f and y_f are the coordinates of front peaks of resin flow. t is for the time of flow, μ for the viscosity, ε for porosity and ΔP for the pressure difference between the front flow and the center of sprue. We can calculate the permeability according to this formula^[7].

After doing the experiments, we can get the data that $V=0.027$ m²/min when time is 60 seconds. Pipe diameter used to inject, represented by D , is 0.01m. The injection pressure, represented by P , is 105000Pa. The content of fiber volume, represented by ϕ , is 0.6. And the resin's viscosity is 0.2Pa · s.

If V is 0.027 m²/min, we can know that the flowing area, A , is 0.027m² in 60 seconds, which is equal to the area of the circle whose radius is x_f centered for O. According to the radial permeability test, inlet pipe is at the center of the circle, and resin flows in all directions from the center entrance. Because resin flows without specific direction, the peak of resin forms a circle. Therefore, there are following formulas^[8]:

$$K_{11} = K_{22}$$

$$x_f = y_f = \sqrt{\frac{A}{\pi}} = \sqrt{\frac{0.027m^2}{3.14}} = 0.0927m$$

$$x_0 = y_0 = D \div 2 = 0.005m \quad (6)$$

Porosity can be calculated by the formula that $\varepsilon = 1 - \phi$, and the final result is 0.4.

Put all these parameters in anisotropic main formula, we can calculate that $K_{11} = K_{22} = 1.387 \times 10^{-10}$.

3.2 Filling Simulation of Foam-Core Sandwich on the Upper Surface

Hull consists of two parts which will be molded separately, and it is designed for symmetric structure, therefore, in order to improve the efficiency of calculation in the process of simulation, we can choose half of the upper and lower parts to calculate. Then take symmetry operations to show the calculation results of the whole hull, which simplifies the

calculation. The settings of simulation parameters are as follows: the content of fiber volume (V_f) is 60%, pipe diameter (D) is 20mm, permeability on the X direction (K_{11}) is $2.7 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^2$ and $2.7 \times 10^{-10} \text{m}^2$ on the Y direction (K_{22}) and injection pressure (P) is $1.01 \times 10^5 \text{Pa}$.

Based on the features of the hull, two kinds of filling schemes are determined. Due to the shape of the hull is more complex, the first scheme shows that we can lay inlet pipe along the blankly lines of the hull, and lay the export pipelines of resin along the outer structure. The layout scheme is shown as figure 3.

Figure 3 The Layout Scheme of the Pipelines on the Surface of Foam

The calculation results of the first scheme are shown in figure 4, figure 5 and figure 6.

Figure 4 The Calculation Results of the Surface of Upper Part by First Scheme

Figure 5 The Calculation Results of the Surface of Lower Part by First Scheme

Figure 6 The Calculation Results of the Pressure Distribution of the Upper and Lower Parts

The second scheme obeys the symmetry principle of center line. We can lay the main pipelines on the center line and then put the subordinate lines over the main pipeline, concentrating on the best length of lines so as to make sure that the resin can reach the boundary exports at the same time. The layout of lines are shown in figure 7.

Figure 7 The Layout Scheme of the Pipelines on the Surface of Foam

The calculation results of the second scheme are shown in figure 8, figure 9 and figure 10.

Figure 8 The Calculation Results of the Surface of Upper Part by Second Scheme

Figure 9 The Calculation Results of the Surface of Lower Part by Second Scheme

Figure 10 The Calculation Results of the Pressure Distribution of the Upper and Lower Parts

Chart 1 The Comparison of Filling Time Between the First and Second Schemes

Schemes	Number of Entrance	Number of Exit	Configuration of Pipelines	Filling Time
First Scheme of Top Surface	5	12	Complex	41min
Second Scheme of Top Surface	3	7	Simple	52.3min
First Scheme of Undersurface	10	29	Complex	28.5min
Second Scheme of Undersurface	3	13	Simple	40.8min

From the emulational results of the first and second schemes we can see that the filling time of the upper and lower parts of the hull by the first scheme is shorter than the second. However, the configuration of pipelines of the first one is more complex and the number of entrance and exit is even more, which is not convenient in actual operations. From figure 4 and figure 5, we can see that the resin assembles in the center of the hull in the first scheme, which puts forward higher requirements for the configuration of exits and their pipelines. If assembled unreasonable, it is easy to form dry spots in the center of the hull. In the second scheme, the configuration of pipelines is simple and the filling time is permitted. Moreover, resin can reach the boundary of molds at the same time, which avoids the waste of resin. Most important, it's difficult to form dry spots in the process of filling and the distribution of pressure is more reasonable. In conclusion, the second scheme is the better one.

3.3 Filling Simulation of Foam-Core Sandwich on the Lower Surface

Because the lower surface of foam attaches to the moulds, we can not arrange honeycomb ducts and the entrances or exits of resin on this surface. Therefore, we need to deal with the foam. We can work out the grooves of honeycomb ducts on the upper or lower surface of the foam-core sandwich. Meanwhile, we can make some deflector holes on the junction of grooves, as shown in figure 11.

Because RTM-Worx software can not directly simulate foam-core sandwich structure, this paper will divide it into two parts, including the upper and lower surfaces of the foam-core sandwich, so as to separately simulate. The upper surface is simulated on the basis of reinforced composites material structure of ordinary fiber. that is the simulation process shown in 3.2. The resin in the lower surface of foam-core sandwich is from the one in the upper surface, which flows through the deflector holes and grooves. The process that resin fills the foam-core sandwich structure is shown in the following figure.

Figure 12 The schematic diagram that resin fills the foam-core sandwich structure

Therefore, on the premise that the entrances of resin and honeycomb ducts can not be arranged on the lower surface of foam-core sandwich, we can regard the grooves on the lower surface as the honeycomb ducts, deflector holes as the entrances of resin and the length of pipelines as the thickness of core on the lower surface of foam-core sandwich. The specific handling method is shown in the figure.

Figure 13 The Schematic Diagram of Resin Flow in the Foam-Core Sandwich Structure
The whole arrangement of pipelines and entrances is shown in figure 14.

Figure 14 The Arrangements of Pipelines, Entrances and Exits on the Lower surfaces of the Upper and Lower Parts of the Hull

According to the feature that resin flows shown in figure 12, the process that resin flows from the upper surface of foam-core sandwich to the lower surface can be arranged by many reasons. For example, we can simulate the filling process of lower surface by controlling the open time of entrances on the lower surface and the open time of entrances that resin flows in on the lower surface can get reference from the flowing simulation results of the upper surface.

Figure 15 The Calculation Results of the lower Surface on the Foam-Core Sandwich of the Upper Hull

Figure 16 The Calculation Results of the lower Surface on the Foam-Core Sandwich of the Lower Hull

Figure 17 The Calculation Results of the Pressure Distribution of the Lower Surfaces of the Upper and Lower Parts of the Hull

The filling time of the upper part of the hull on the lower surface of the foam-core sandwich is 288 seconds, and the lower part is 345 seconds, which proves that the filling time that resin flows into the lower surface from the upper surface through the deflector holes is very short. Therefore, the filling time of the whole foam-core sandwich structure can learn from the filling time of the upper surface. Due to the lesser interval among the grooves and thickness among deflector holes, it's effective to avoid the occurrence of the dry spots as well as make it possible to fill the whole lower surface of foam-core sandwich quickly and efficiently. Form figure 17, we can see that the center pressure between the upper and lower parts of the hull is higher with lower in the boundary, which reflects the reasonability of pressure distribution.

CONCLUSION

1. As to these solid Tri-body composites boat who has large size and complex shape, scheme two that laying main pipeline along the axis and tubes in a symmetry structure is more reasonable, which can effectively reduce the formation of dry spots as well as the waste of resin.
2. As to the simulation of composites in VARTM possessing of foam-core sandwich structure, we can separate the foam into upper and lower surfaces to conduct. The upper and lower surfaces are in accordance with the solid composites to simulate, and the grooves with deflector holes can be replaced by tubes. Meanwhile, the setting of opening time of deflector holes on the lower surface can get reference from the filling flow of upper surface.
3. Because the foam-core sandwich is divided into two parts to calculate, there will some errors in the filling time and estimates of resin's usage. However, the prediction about the trend of composites in VARTM resin filling flow of foam-core sandwich has a practical significance, which can guide the actual production.
4. The simulation method of foam-core sandwich structure put forward in this paper can use RTM-Wrox software to conduct efficient calculation of complex and large construction members of foam-core sandwich structure. The simulation results can guide the actual process of forming the layout of the pipelines, entrances and exits.

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